

SO YOU'RE IN A SPOT OF BOTHER...

Well, you are not the first and certainly won't be the last. So keep your hopes up - whether you make it out alive or not will largely come down to you, your attitude and actions.

Ok, first things first, RELAX. Take a deep breath and keep a clear head. The mistakes that many people make in a life or death situation is getting their priorities wrong. Think before you act. A phrase you can use to remind yourself is; Please remember what's first - **PROTECTION, RESCUE, WATER, FOOD**. These are the absolute basics you need to survive, and survival now needs to become your number one goal. So here you go - down to business.

FIRE

Fire will provide you with heat, light, comfort and protection. There are many ways to light your tinder even in the rain or cold. A lighter, matches, fire striker or car battery are simple options.

Choose the location of your fire wisely. Relative proximity to your shelter and wind direction being the most important considerations. Build a base of green branches if the ground is wet or dig a pit to protect it if it is windy. A fire requires only three ingredients - **OXYGEN, FUEL, HEAT**. Gather and organise your fuel, big and small, before you start your fire! Look for wood that is off the ground to ensure your best chance of it being dry. Dead branches and twigs crack when you break them. You will need tinder to get your spark going. Fluffy fibrous materials like dry moss, grasses, cotton balls and tampons are great tinder. Once you have got a flame, you must keep it going. Be sure that you have gathered all the fuel you need in advance. You can keep a fire smouldering throughout the night by covering it up with ash or dry soil.

✂️ 2 RESCUE

Rescue is your next priority. Rescue services will start looking for you as soon as they know you are missing. You may only get one chance. Don't mess it up.

LOCATION

Put yourself in the shoes of the rescuers. What way will they be coming from? How will they spot you? If it is safe to do so **STAY WHERE YOU ARE!** If you have a vehicle, stay near it. Too many people die by heading off into the unknown, only to be found dead within 5 miles of their car. Be smart and make yourself safe and visible.

SIGNALLING

Lay out stones and objects to create an SOS bear your location. If you have light or pyrotechnics have them near at hand and ready to use. Any shiny surface can reflect sunlight for many miles to rescuers. Use the light to signal them directly or sweep the horizon if none is in sight. Smokey signal fires can also alert rescuers. Have them built and ready for quick ignition. Keep the fire dry by covering it with vegetation and have some damp or living wood/leaves nearby to create smoke (you can use oil, diesel or car tyres to make smoke as well).

✂️ 1 PROTECTION

From the elements, dangerous animals or imminent hazards. Protection is your number one priority in a survival situation.

CLOTHING

Clothing is your first line of defence against the climate. So wear or improvise clothing. In the cold, layers are warmer than just one thick garment. Keep your bodies core warm. Headwear is important. A golden rule of cold weather survival - **ACT BEFORE YOU ARE TOO COLD!** Avoid sweating and keep your clothing dry. Wet clothing can lose up to 90% of its insulating properties. (Water conducts heat away from your body 25 times faster than air of the same temperature). Keeping your clothes dry from sweat as well as the elements is **VITAL**.

In a hot climate, clothing and headwear may be your main protection from the sun. Keep skin covered to prevent burning. An improvised hat or headscarf can provide shade and keep the body cool if made wet (think urine or other liquid fluids you can find - survival ain't pretty!).

SHELTER

Shelter is top priority in any environment. As with every element of survival, you must think carefully before expending precious **ENERGY. DON'T WASTE TIME CONSTRUCTING A SHELTER IF NATURE HAS ALREADY PROVIDED ONE.** Take advantage of caves, overhangs, hollows and trees. In many situations a man made shelter may exist - A life raft, abandoned structures etc. Man made materials can be scavenged to help in construction. Location is everything. Protection from the elements is the first key in shelter. It needs to be stable and away from natural hazards such as rain, flooding, rock falls, animals and insect swarms. Study the terrain before choosing your shelter location.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE
Without day-light saving

With day-light saving

SOUTHERN HEMISPHERE
Without day-light saving

With day-light saving

DIRECTION

To use your watch as compass in the Northern Hemisphere, point the hour hand at the sun. The imaginary line bisecting the hour hand and 12 o'clock is your north/south line. Not accurate in latitudes below 20 degrees. In the Southern Hemisphere, point 12 o'clock at the sun and then bisect that and the hour hand.

✂ 3 WATER

To be rescued or to self-rescue, you need **WATER**. Without water, your survival time is numbered in days, at best.

SOURCES

Follow game trails, animals or insects to surface water sources like rivers and streams. Look for lush vegetation as a sign that underground water may be present. Melt snow or ice. Plants and vegetation can provide fluids - even animals in extreme situations. Sucking liquid out of a fish eye may not seem appetising, but it may just save you.

COLLECTION

NEVER WAIT UNTIL YOU ARE WITHOUT WATER TO BEGIN COLLECTING IT!

Act whilst you are still fresh and have some supplies. Use any materials you have to aid in the collection of water. Large leaves can be used to trap rain or dew. Condensation from damp ground or vegetation can be captured with a solar still. Be inventive - It is one of the keys to good survival. **IMPROVISE, ADAPT, OVERCOME.**

PURIFICATION

Water from arctic ice (caution: may be sea ice), a rain/dew trap or solar still will not need purifying, but other sources may. Always purify water when possible. Drinking water that makes you sick can be worse than water at all, as it can make you weak and dehydrated. Boil water for 5 minutes if you are at higher elevations. (At sea level is okay to boil water for just a minute and then you avoid wasting fuel through excessive boiling). Basic filtration can be achieved through a shirt or coffee filter; again: **IMPROVISE, ADAPT, OVERCOME.**

DISCLAIMER & WARNING:
USE SURVIVAL TECHNIQUES AND EQUIPMENT AT YOUR OWN RISK.

Even with proper training and preparation, survival situations are inherently dangerous and can result in injury or death. This guide and limitless equipment, South West Survival cannot address all survival situations and cannot guarantee your survival or prevent injuries. When venturing into the wilderness, it is your responsibility to have proper training, preparation, information, experience and equipment. Because any survival situation can expose you to unpredictable hazards or risks, South West Survival are not responsible for any injury, death or consequences of any actions taken on the basis of the information provided in this guide, and do not suggest or guarantee that the use of this guide or these products will prevent these risks.

✂ 4 FOOD

Once you have protection, rescue and water covered, you need **FOOD**. Food provides vital energy to help you survive.

SNARES & TRAPS

HUNTING WILD ANIMALS SHOULD NOT BE YOUR FIRST THOUGHT WHEN LOOKING FOR FOOD.

Instead, snares and traps will use up less energy. Most animals can be snared with a wire noose in the right position, such as near a den or above a game trail. Don't set it too close to a den as animals are wary when they first emerge from hiding. Also remember: Funnel the animal toward your trap. Camouflage the snare then bait it. The more traps you set, the better your chance of success. If there are rivers or other bodies of water nearby, these should be the first places you look for food.

SCAVENGING

The good survivor is a scavenger. Letting nature do the hard work, is the best way to find food. Try to eat anything you can get your hands on that is safe - you can't be choosy - you don't know where/what your next meal will be. Generally if it walks, crawls, swims or flies, it can be eaten! Think smart. Your brain is bigger than every animal or insect (or at least it should be!). When storing food, be sure that it is out of reach of any animals or insects it may attract.

KNOTS

There is no secret to the art of knot tying - just practice and patience. A few basic knots can be provided a multitude of uses in a survival situation. Remember KISS: **KEEP IT SIMPLE STUPID!** There is not much you can't do, with these simple knots below:

FIGURE 8 KNOT

CLOVE HITCH KNOT

BOWLINE KNOT

